

Chemical examination of *Citrus pectinifera* juice

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Abstract : Phytochemical study of *Citrus pectinifera* juice has resulted in the isolation of three compounds : nobiletin, dotriacontanol and hexadecandioic acid. Nobiletin is already a known compound from the juice of *C. pectinifera*. The other two known compounds namely hexadecandioic acid and dotriacontanol are being reported for the first time from the juice of this plant. Biochemical parameters in the juice were found to be comparable with those of Mandarin species.

Keywords : *Citrus pectinifera*, Rutaceae, nobiletin, dotriacontanol, hexadecandioic, biochemical parameters.

Introduction

Citrus pectinifera (*C. depressa*, Fam : Rutaceae) is also known as Taiwan tangerine, flat lemon, hiram lemon or thin-skinned flat lemon. The tree is vigorous, round-topped and finely stemmed. The fruit is very small and orange coloured, oblate and highly depressed at both ends with very thin, loose and aromatic rind. A recent study indicates that nobiletin a polymethoxylated flavone, accumulated in shiikuwasha fruits (*C. depressa* Hayata), exhibits anticarcinogenic activity¹. It also regulates the production of pro-matrix metalloproteinase and interferes with the proliferation of synovial fibroblast suggesting that it may serve as a drug to maintain articular cartilage and osteoarthritis pannus formation in rheumatoid arthritis². The plant is known to have a very high medicinal value. Flowers are stimulant, diuretic, disinfectant. The essential oil of the plant is known to contain flavones.

In view of scanty data on the chemical components of *C. pectinifera* juice, we have undertaken the present investigation. Three compounds have been isolated and characterized. Biochemical parameters have also been determined.

Results and discussion

Dotriacontanol (1) was obtained on elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1). It was crystallized out from chloroform. The IR spectrum of the compound showed the presence of hydroxyl group (3303 cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound in CDCl₃ revealed a triplet (*J* 7.5 Hz) at δ 3.63 integrating to two protons, which could

be due to a methylene bearing oxygenation. A broad signal at δ 1.57, integrating to two protons, could be due to a methylene β to oxygenation. Another broad signal at δ 1.25, for fifty eight protons, could be due to twenty nine methylenes. There was a triplet (*J* 7.5 Hz) at δ 0.88 integrating for three protons which could be due to a terminal methyl group. The compound could be characterized as dotriacontanol (1). The observed molecular mass of the compound lends support to this conclusion. The observed data for this compound was consistent with literature data³ for dotriacontanol (1).

Nobiletin (2) was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 9). It responded to colour reaction with Mg/HCl hinting it to be a flavone. The IR spectrum of the compound showed a peak at 1646 cm⁻¹ suggesting a α,β-unsaturated carbonyl group in the compound. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound in CDCl₃ showed a double doublet (*J* 7.5 and 2.5 Hz) at δ 7.57 integrating to one proton, which could be H-6' of a flavone having substituents at C-3' and C-4'. A doublet (*J* 2.5 Hz) at δ 7.42 integrating to one proton could be H-2'. Another doublet (*J* 7.5 Hz) observed at δ 6.99 integrating to one proton could be H-5' of the flavone. There was singlet at δ 6.63 integrating to one proton, which could be H-3. There were five singlets at δ 4.11 (3H), 4.03 (3H), 3.98 (3H), 3.97 (3H) and 3.96 (6H) indicating six methoxy groups. The compound could thus be characterized as 5,6,7,8,3',4'-hexamethoxy flavone (2). The observed properties of this compound were consistent with literature data³ for 5,6,7,8,3',4'-hexamethoxy flavone (2).

Hexadecandioic acid (3) was obtained upon elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 3). It was crystallized from methanol. It gives brisk effervescence with sodium bicarbonate solution suggesting it to be a carboxylic acid. The IR spectrum of the compound suggested the presence of carbonyl (1747 cm^{-1}) and hydroxyl (3293 cm^{-1}) groups. The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum of the compound in CDCl_3 showed a triplet ($J\ 7.5\ \text{Hz}$) at $\delta\ 2.17$ integrating to four protons, which could be due to two identical methylenes α to a carbonyl group. There was a broad signal at $\delta\ 1.56$, for twenty four protons, which could be due to twelve methylenes. The data obtained for this compound was consistent with literature data³ for hexadecane-1,16-dioic acid (3).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined on Ganson apparatus. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) spectra were recorded on Bruker AC-300F (300 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on Hitachi 570 spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were recorded on VG-70S 11-250 J GC-MS-DS spectrometer.

C. pectinifera fruits (5 kg) were collected from Department of Horticulture, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar. Fruits were squeezed to get juice. The juice was divided into two parts. One part of the juice was washed with ethyl acetate four times. The extract so obtained was concentrated on water bath under reduced pressure to obtain viscous mass. The viscous mass thus obtained was mixed with silica gel (60–120 mesh), dried on water bath and subjected to silica gel (60–120 mesh) column chromatography with solvents of increasing polarity and three compounds were isolated.

Another part of the juice was used for determining biochemical parameters tannins⁴, total sugars⁵, titrable acidity⁷, TSS and ascorbic acid contents in the juices of *C. pectinifera* as per standard methods.

Dotriacontanol (1) : It was obtained on elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1). It was crystallized out from chloroform as colourless solid, 18 mg, m.p. $90\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (lit.³ m.p. $89\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; IR ν_{max} (nujol) 719, 730, 799, 1021, 1102, 1261, 1411, 1462, 1473, 2847, 2916, 3303 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) $\delta\ 3.63$ (2H, t, $J\ 7.5\ \text{Hz}$, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-O}$), 1.57 (2H, s, br, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-O}$), 1.25 (58H, s, br, $29 \times \text{CH}_2$), 0.88 (3H, t, $J\ 7.5\ \text{Hz}$, CH_3); EIMS m/z (% abundance) 324 (M^+ , 100), 343 (37), 399 (11), 416 (62), 418 (24), 452 (12), 466 (5).

Nobiletin (2) : The compound was obtained on elution

with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 9) and was crystallized from methanol, 40 mg, m.p. $135\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (lit.³ m.p. $134\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). It gave yellow colour with Mg/HCl ; IR ν_{max} (nujol) 581, 621, 680, 801, 838, 1015, 1079, 1111, 1646, 2838, 2940 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) $\delta\ 7.57$ (1H, dd, $J\ 7.5, 2.5\ \text{Hz}$, H-6'), 7.42 (1H, d, $J\ 2.5\ \text{Hz}$, H-2'), 6.99 (1H, d, $J\ 7.5\ \text{Hz}$, H-5'), 6.63 (1H, s, H-3), 4.11 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.03 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.98 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.97 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.96 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$); EIMS m/z (% abundance) 402 (M^+ , 100), 394 (25), 372 (55).

Hexadecandioic acid (3) : It was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 3). It was crystallized from methanol, 15 mg, m.p. $125\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (lit.³ m.p. $126\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). It gave brisk effervescence with sodium bicarbonate solution; IR ν_{max} (nujol) 506, 548, 598, 818, 881, 943, 1080, 1147, 1174, 1242, 1359, 1391, 1428, 1747, 2565, 2643, 2771, 3293 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) $\delta\ 2.17$ (4H, t, $J\ 7.5\ \text{Hz}$, $2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{-CO}$), 1.56 (24H, br, s, $12 \times \text{CH}_2$); EIMS m/z (% abundance) 286 (M^+ , 10), 216 (21), 212 (100), 194 (49), 174 (63), 168 (28), 100 (24).

The juice of *C. pectinifera* contained sugars (23.3 g/100 ml)⁷, tannins (0.02 mg/100 ml)⁸, ascorbic acid (18.46 mg/100 ml)⁹, TSS (12.15%)⁹ and titrable acidity (12.16 g/100 ml)⁹.

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